

SACRO in a Federated Ecosystem

PANORAMA Work Package 3 Final Report

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Executive Summary

This report presents the findings of PANORAMA Work Package 3, which evaluated the Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs (SACRO) tools and examined their potential role in supporting Output Statistical Disclosure Control (OSDC) both within individual Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and across federated networks.

Through testing, ACRO was found to perform well for supported analytical methods, offering consistent, auditable disclosure checks and an accessible workflow for researchers. SACRO Viewer demonstrated strong usability and reliability for reviewing ACRO outputs, approving or rejecting files for release, and generating controlled output packages. However, testing identified several limitations, including issues with suppression logic, certain errors arising from specific ACRO methods, and support for users to save output checking in progress.

In parallel with technical assessment, PANORAMA conducted interviews and consultations across TREs to produce Federated OSDC Principles—guidance outlining the operational, governance, and policy alignments required to safely and consistently conduct output checking in a federated context. This work highlights that federated OSDC poses significant operational challenges that cannot be solved through technology alone.

The report also evaluates whether SACRO could act as one of the “sets of eyes” in the Four Eyes Principle in OSDC. SACRO can provide a reliable, standardised first-pass assessment but

cannot replace the contextual judgement of a human reviewer. Its most appropriate current role is as a supporting tool to enhance, rather than substitute for, expert oversight.

Overall, SACRO shows strong potential to improve efficiency, consistency, and transparency in OSDC processes, particularly for high-volume or routine outputs. Realising this potential at scale will require further development of the tools, clearer standards for federated operation, and coordinated governance across TREs.

1. Background: Federated Analytics

1.1. Output checking in Trusted Research Environments

Sensitive data research requires stringent safeguards to ensure that published outputs do not permit disclosure of individuals. To enable this, secure environments known as Trusted Research Environments (TREs) are used. When researchers wish to export results (covering all forms of analysed data including tables, statistical summaries, plots, etc. as well as code or machine learning models) from a TRE, release of those outputs must be carefully checked to guard against any risk of re-identification or disclosure. This final stage – known as Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) and more specifically Output Statistical Disclosure Control (OSDC) – is often a major bottleneck (Smith et al., 2023). In TREs, every output is subject to manual review by expert staff. This manual checking is time-consuming, labour-intensive, and can delay the timely release of research outputs.

Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs (SACRO) is a tool developed under Phase 1 of DARE UK to address precisely the bottleneck caused by manual output checking in TREs. The Toolkit comprises several components: (1) A library of ‘drop in’ commands that run simultaneously for standard data analysis that automatically run SDC checks on the outputs; (2) a user interface that presents both the research output and the results of the disclosure risk; and (3) supporting documentation to support SDC generally, as well as the rationale behind the automated assessments. These tools were developed to support consistency across TREs, which is crucial for a number of reasons. First, there is a duty of care to protect sensitive personal data - and if there is inconsistency in application of SDC, it may be the case that analysed outputs could lead to re-identification of individuals. For researchers, it is critical that they are subject to consistency in SDC across organisations so that analyses released from one environment will also be released consistently from any other environments.

1.2. The SACRO tool

As introduced above, SACRO is a software toolkit designed to assist Trusted Research Environments (TREs) in performing Output Statistical Disclosure Control (OSDC). It automates checks for common disclosure risks in statistical outputs and provides structured, auditable feedback to human reviewers. SACRO is developed as an open-source, modular system that can be deployed across heterogeneous TREs.

SACRO consists of three primary components:

- **SACRO Code Libraries:** Language-specific libraries (Python, R, Stata) provide “drop-in” replacements for commonly used statistical analysis functions. These wrappers automatically execute the requested statistical operation (e.g., generating tables, models, plots), run disclosure control checks on the resulting output and attach

metadata describing the checks performed and their results. These libraries are intended to be used directly within secure computing environments, requiring no external connectivity.

- SACRO Output Checker Engine: The core checking logic is implemented as a rule-based engine. It evaluates outputs against a configurable set of SDC rules, including: minimum cell-count thresholds, dominance checks (e.g., maximum contribution of any one individual), histograms, high-risk summary statistics (e.g., extremely small N, detailed cross-tabulations). Rules and thresholds are configurable to align with local TRE policy. The engine outputs:
 - A structured JSON report
 - A risk classification (pass / warn / fail)
 - Metadata linking results to the specific analysis command and environment
- SACRO Output Viewer: A lightweight user interface (UI) enables human output checkers to review the original output (rendered safely within the TRE), SACRO's automated assessment, highlighted risk flags and rule-level explanations and suggested mitigations (e.g., suppressing values, aggregating categories).

Critically, the Viewer provides an auditable human-machine interface but leaves final release decisions to human checkers.

1.3. PANORAMA: Output checking in a federated ecosystem

Whilst the early iteration of SACRO looked at implementation and utility within individual TREs in Phase 1, it only briefly considered the concept of 'federation'. However, it is essential to consider how SDC generally should be approached in a federation, and how SACRO can be used to support collaboration among multiple TREs. For output checking, the two main approaches to federation, 'data pooling' (i.e., moving datasets into a single location for analysis), and 'federated analytics' (i.e., moving analyses to distributed datasets) each pose interesting challenges for SDC and SACRO. The importance of coordinating the output-checking process without compromising privacy or security, whilst streamlining processes to be scalable, efficient and responsive to researchers' needs is essential. However, it is also complicated, and without robust approaches and alignment, particularly around operational processes, federated output checking may compromise patient privacy and hinder efficient release of research data from federated partners.

PANORAMA Work Package 3 considers whether SACRO can be used to support output checking in a federated context, aiming to understand the extent to which semi-automated output-checking tools can support secure, scalable research across multiple Trusted Research Environments (TREs). Specifically, the project seeks to:

- Assess the technical integration across heterogeneous TREs participating in PANORAMA.
- Examine the effectiveness for output statistical disclosure control.
- Evaluate the usability and practicality of use within a federation.
- Understand implications for governance and consistency of SDC within a federation at scale.
- Evaluate potential efficiency gains from implementing SACRO within a federated context.

1.4. Work performed

For testing of tools, we tested ACRO library, SACRO-Viewer and both tools together in an end-to-end pipeline (how ACRO and the viewer work together). For each tool, we performed several types of testing, defined at Section 2 below. These include functional and non-functional testing, and positive and negative testing. We also consider the operational context of the checking workflow and how current SACRO tools map to that process.

Over the course of this work, we carried out a detailed assessment of output-checking practices across the federated PANORAMA network and other TRevolution Early Adopters, [VISTA](#) and [SOCRATES](#). This resulted in the development of a set of principles for federated output checking.

In parallel, we evaluated the role of SACRO within the Four Eyes Principle, examining whether its semi-automated checks could credibly serve as one of the required independent assessments in TRE output-release workflows.

1.5. Structure of the report

This report is structured to provide a comprehensive evaluation of SACRO within the PANORAMA federation. We begin with an overview of the output checking workflow and use cases for SACRO tooling in the Secure Data Environments (SDEs). We then present our testing protocol and results of the effectiveness of SACRO, considering its ability to identify and flag disclosure risks. We include an evaluation of the usability and practicality of SACRO from the perspective of both researchers and output checkers working within a federated workflow. The report also explores the governance implications of adopting SACRO for federated output checking, focusing on its potential to support disclosure-control practices as well as its current limitations. Finally, we examine whether there are potential efficiency gains associated with implementing SACRO in a federated context.

2. Assessment of ACRO Package

2.1. Introduction

Semi-automated Checking of Research Outputs, or SACRO, tools are a group of tools designed to help researchers evaluate research outputs for disclosure risk. They include ACRO, a python package performing automated checks for disclosure risks; and SACRO-Viewer, a user interface to easily visualise the results of ACRO checks and process disclosure decisions before potential export of analyses.

ACRO is a python package maintained by the University of the West of England that aims to support researchers by applying automated checks to tabular and statistical outputs. It provides a number of python commands to generate tabular and statistical output with disclosure checking results attached to the outputs. It also provides commands to export outputs from the python environment with the attached disclosure checking results in a .json file, intended to be ingested by SACRO-Viewer. (See [Table A1, Appendix A](#) for a full list of commands.) The report may contain exception requests, general comments and automated disclosure check results. These can then be reviewed by the researcher or someone else via the SACRO-viewer.

Figure 1: High level ACRO workflow. User-submitted code is executed in ACRO, analysed securely, checked through disclosure-risk testing, suppression applied if needed, and analyses with checking results are returned to the user.

A key point to note is around the role of suppression in the ACRO package. ACRO provides the option to suppress risky outputs when generating analyses for export. For example, certain cells in a summary table may be suppressed due to being based on a small count of observations. All outputs have statistical disclosure checks applied and results included in the report automatically, regardless of whether suppression is applied.

Users have the option to export analytical output with or without suppression already applied. With suppression, outputs *should* be passing statistical disclosure checks. This is because ACRO has configurable checking parameters that can be set to organisational standards (or cross-organisational standards in a federated setting, for example). Without suppression, outputs may or may not pass disclosure checks.

2.2. Use cases

What kinds of research does ACRO support?

ACRO currently supports analysis of data processed to generate tabular or tabular-based analytical outputs, plus classical statistical models that ingest tabular data (including data that has been converted to tabular form). Specifically, it supports the generation of summary tables including cross-tabulation, histograms, classical statistical models (OLS and binary-dependent variable models (Logit/Probit)) and survival analysis. It does not currently extend to other models or visualisations.

Current requirements for research

The PANORAMA partners include the Yorkshire & Humber NHS Secure Data Environment (at the time of testing, the platform infrastructure for Yorkshire & Humber SDE was hosted at the University of Sheffield), the North East North Cumbria NHS Secure Data Environment, and the North West NHS Secure Data Environment. All three are cloud-based TRE infrastructures, with different platform providers and configurations. The current use cases for all three partners are health-related research. Datasets utilised in health research can vary dramatically in their characteristics. In general data may be not only tabular data but also non-tabular data such as images and free-text documents. The current use cases are limited to tabular health datasets, with imaging and free-text outside the scope of testing. Tabular data can be very sparse, have many missing values, generally contains a mixture of numerical and categorical data types, and can be very large, with hundreds (if not thousands) of columns and potentially millions of rows. Ideally, output checking tooling would support data with these characteristics.

In terms of the kinds of analysis utilised by researchers using tabular data, the breadth of models and approaches to summarisation and visualisation extend beyond methods currently available in ACRO (and supported by the Viewer). These include more complex statistical and machine learning models, as well as alternative graphical outputs e.g. common plot types such as scatter, box, bar/line and pies and more advanced visualisations.

It is noted that the SACRO toolkit includes SACRO-ML, which provides additional modelling coverage for trained machine learning models, however SACRO-ML coverage has not been investigated as part of this exercise.

2.2.1. Assumptions regarding end users

Users currently utilising the three PANORAMA partner infrastructures to perform research typically have the following relevant profile:

1. Comfortable with using command line for installation
2. Able to use Jupyter / python / pandas / statsmodels (python library) to generate statistical analysis / graphical outputs
3. Able to use R to generate the same statistical analysis / graphical output

For the purpose of testing usability of SACRO tooling for a typical case, our assumption is that researchers have the competencies above.

2.3. Testing Goal

There are several areas of ACRO testing encompassing usability, performance, suitability for research support for typical, feasibility for use, and accuracy/correctness of SDC checking (comparison of local environment results to expected results).

The overarching goal is to assess the strengths and limitations of the ACRO tool (in combination with the viewer) for supporting SDC by researchers and reviewers in a practical setting. We expect that ACRO will primarily be used by researchers to generate output, while the SACRO Viewer is used by both researchers and reviewers to process ACRO output. Thus, testing for ACRO is structured around how it would be used by a typical researcher. We also consider ACRO checking results from the perspective of a reviewer, however this is discussed more extensively in Section 3 (testing of the SACRO-Viewer).

2.4. Testing Approach

Testing is designed to assess usability with tabular data that address the most common characteristics mentioned above. Specifically, we perform core functional testing using a small, 'clean', publicly available dataset. We then adapt that dataset to conduct further tests with more observations, missing values and incorrect data types.

Whilst all partners installed and tested SACRO in their respective environments, detailed, systematic tests were conducted on the Yorkshire & Humber SDE platform hosted by the University of Sheffield (at the time of testing), with some exploratory testing conducted on a local machine. Full configuration details for testing are provided in Appendix A. Testing was completed in Python for two of the partners (including University of Sheffield) and one partner tested ACRO-R. All feedback covers both Python and R.

Tests can be grouped into the following categories.

2.4.1. Functional and non-functional

Functional testing aims to compare actual outputs to expected behaviours. That is, it asks whether the software fundamentally performs the functions it is supposed to do, or does it do 'the right thing?'. An example would be testing whether a statistic was calculated correctly from underlying data.

Non-functional testing aims to evaluate how the software performs the above, or does it do things 'the right way?'. An example would be testing how the software handles larger datasets.

2.4.2. Positive versus negative tests

The difference between positive and negative tests lies in the inputs. Positive testing aims to evaluate whether the software generates the expected results given valid inputs. Similar to the above, an example would be testing that an average value is correctly calculated when given valid, numeric data. In contrast, negative testing aims to evaluate whether invalid inputs will be correctly handled. An example would be testing that the software correctly throws an error when trying to calculate the average value for categorical (non-numeric) data.

Each of these groups is important for a tool aiming for use by researchers, since the tool needs to produce correct results, and correctly handle common problems such as messy data, as well as be practical for researchers to use in their operating environment. It is immediately clear that negative testing in particular can potentially be extensive, since the definitions of invalid inputs/scenarios can be almost arbitrarily broad. So, it is important to identify the most likely invalid inputs that may occur for the specific use case and prioritise testing around those.

We conducted both positive and negative tests for each of functional and non-functional test groupings. Given the high level goals and typical use cases above, the testing performed can be summarised as follows:

- For functional testing, we assess whether data analysis and statistical modelling methods, termed 'analytical methods' generate results as expected (with and without suppression) and non-analytical methods (methods to manage and export outputs) for correct execution. We generate outputs for each analytical method implemented including key variations and perform some limited comparison of these to the equivalent outputs generated directly in the underlying python packages. For the most part, we cover variations/combinations systematically and, where spot-testing only is performed, this is made clear.

- We focus on positive testing for functional testing but also perform negative testing for a more limited set of analytical outputs, with and without suppression. This is focused on handling missing values and invalid data types.
- For non-functional testing we focus on practical aspects for researchers i.e. installation, usability and sustainability in a secure data environment, usability within a research workflow, support for large datasets and so on.
- We utilise an off-the-shelf dataset requiring minimal preparation - this allows us to invest time in more testing, rather than data pre-processing. It also allows us to easily perform 'controlled experiments'.
- We adapt the dataset in various ways for additional testing around support for larger datasets and invalid inputs.

There is some overlap between testing of ACRO and end-to-end testing for non-analytical methods (and similar for end-to-end testing and SACRO-Viewer testing). Results are cross-referenced where relevant.

2.5. Testing scope and limitations

Testing is not intended to be extensive enough to cover all edge cases or comprehensively identify software errors ('bugs'). Similarly, we do not attempt to evaluate the statistical approach to output checking in terms of mathematical methodology.

Notwithstanding the above, we do attempt to cover a reasonable amount of testing for realistic use cases and make note of a number of software issues identified.

2.5.1. Note on testing individual outputs versus a group of outputs

The tests below apply to tests for individual (one-off) outputs generated via ACRO. There is a separate question around disclosure risk across multiple outputs produced from the same dataset. However, disclosure risk assessment across multiple outputs is not currently supported by ACRO, so testing does not cover this case.

However, some simple examples of how disclosure risk across multiple outputs can occur without being identified by ACRO can be easily generated as shown below.

output_0_0.csv			
ColW	A	B	C
F	50	1	1

(a) low count variables B and C correctly flagged (total count = 52)

output_0_0.csv	
ColW	A
F	50

(b) Count for variable A only approved for disclosure

output_3_0.csv	
ColW	1
F	52

(c) Total count approved for disclosure

output_1_0.csv	
ColW	AB
F	51

(d) Total count for A+B only approved for disclosure but together with (b) or (c) may be disclosive

Figure 2: Individual tables (e.g. counts) may be non-disclosive and individually identified as safe by a checking tool, but together may be disclosive. In this example, (d) together with (b) or (c) could be disclosive.

2.6. Summary of Test Results

Detailed testing performed and individual test results are provided at [Appendix A](#). High level qualitative results and observations are as follows:

1. Analytical methods generate outputs as expected when suppression is not utilised (functional, positive testing)
2. No new issues were identified through functional, negative testing for analytical methods
3. However, when suppression is applied, some outputs generate with errors or not at all (e.g., histograms, crosstab tables). Suppression also did not always operate consistently across outputs e.g. for tables only some cells may be suppressed, while for equivalent histograms the entire output may be suppressed.
4. For non-analytical functional testing, methods execute as expected and correctly export reports and outputs.
5. However, as part of end-to-end testing, a potential issue was identified with the `finalise()` method (this is the method used to generate the final outputs folder and associated `.json` report for passing to the viewer). Specifically, where `finalise()` is executed twice in a row, an error occurs in SACRO-Viewer, with outputs unable to be rendered. The exact source of this issue was not identified and further investigation is required.
6. Non-functional testing.
 - a. The ACRO package performs well in terms of non-functional tests. We spot tested analytical functions with up to 1 million rows with no noticeable issues within the operating environments tested.
 - b. The package is well supported with documentation and follows standard coding conventions, making it easy for researchers familiar with standard python packages to utilise.
 - c. Installation and usability were very straightforward and user friendly for both Linux (Ubuntu) and Windows operating systems. However, we note that for airlocked TREs some additional steps are necessary e.g. adding ACRO to internal python package mirrors. In the longer term, it is possible to add ACRO to standard research workspace images.
 - d. We noted that substituting or amending the suppression config file (`.yaml`) was the only way to change the suppression parameters, however documentation suggests the intention is there to allow amendment via variables. Directly amending the file manually could introduce errors and make it more difficult for researchers and reviewers to track changes.
7. More broadly, we note that ACRO currently supports only a limited set of analyses and variations out of the broad range of use cases that could arise across organisations. However, for critical use cases like generating tabular (or tabular-equivalent) output in particular, it is very useful in reducing time taken to perform disclosure checks.

2.7. Recommendations

Given the testing results above, we identified the following areas where development of the ACRO library could be useful.

1. Supporting more options and flexibility for the analytical functionality already in place. Rather than expand ACRO to new types of analyses, it could be highly valuable to extend around the core methods already in place. For example, supporting more graphing options for similar, tabular results, or supporting more statistical models where the same degrees-of-freedom tests can be applied. This could include wrappers around closely related functions in python packages other than pandas and statsmodels.
2. Review how suppression logic is implemented given the various limitations identified. As we came across some issues around this functionality, the approach to implementation may benefit from some iteration.
3. Clarify and/or review options for amending key disclosure parameters in the config file. The current approach of requiring users to locate and directly amend the default config file could be made easier for users, avoid the introduction of errors and make tracking changes easier.
4. Extension to multiple outputs being jointly evaluated, for tabular outputs in particular. As noted above, ACRO supports checking of outputs 'in isolation' but does not extend to checking multiple outputs together for disclosure risks arising from combined release. However, this is a time-consuming checking process for expert reviewers. If possible, support for checking across multiple outputs - even limited to specific methods such as commonly used tables - could be very useful for reviewers.

3. Assessment of SACRO Viewer Tool

3.1. Introduction

The SACRO-Viewer is a desktop application that allows review of outputs produced by ACRO and other tools in the [AI-SDC](#) toolkit. It ingests .json files generated by ACRO that contain results for automated statistical disclosure checks, and provides a graphical user interface for visualisation of these results. It also provides a way for users to manage and track the process for approval of outputs for release and egress from the trusted research environment.

As for the ACRO package, there are several areas of testing for SACRO-Viewer encompassing functional performance, usability, performance, suitability for research support for typical use cases, and feasibility for use in the Ronin Core and Ronin Isolate environments.

The overarching goal is to assess the strengths and limitations of SACRO-Viewer (in combination with ACRO) for supporting SDC by researchers and reviewers in a practical setting. Testing for SACRO-Viewer is structured around how it would be used by a typical researcher or reviewer, with a particular emphasis on reviewing

Detailed testing steps and results are provided at [Appendix B](#). The following sections give an overview of the testing areas and approach, and summarise key findings.

3.2. Use Cases

A key consideration in assessing the viewer is whether its primary user group is researchers or TRE output checking staff (or potentially a combination of these two user groups). The needs of these user groups will differ significantly in terms of features and functionality needed and most useful for checking workflows. A typical checking workflow incorporates both initial self-checking by researchers (mandatory in some organisations) before submitting a request to egress outputs, followed by checking by an expert, independent reviewer ('reviewing'). An

example workflow for reviewing outputs, based on current SDE practice, is shown at Figure 3 below.

Output Statistical Disclosure Control Workflow

Figure 3: OSDC workflow: Researchers submit an output request. One or more rounds of review including various disclosure checks are performed by one or more reviewers. This may involve rework by researchers. (Source: Pallister et al, 2025)

Importantly for the SACRO-Viewer tool, the workflow will involve the same outputs and checking results being passed back and forth between multiple users and user groups and may include rework and resubmission by researchers. There may also be a divergence in preferences between researchers (who may prefer small, incremental reviews) and the reviewing team (which may prefer a single, large review).

For large sets of outputs, the reviewing task may be split among multiple reviewers or performed in 'chunks'. Multiple reviewers may be required over the course of a project due to staff availability. Conferral between reviewers may also be needed or desired. A key consideration therefore must be the functionality and workflows based on multiple user groups, with functionality for researchers and TRE output checkers having significantly different requirements. Ongoing development of SACRO requires all potential user groups and workflows to be identified and scoped appropriately to ensure the appropriate development.

3.3. Testing Approach

SACRO Viewer has several areas of core functionality that it is designed to provide, as mentioned above. Specifically (a) displaying outputs produced in ACRO, (b) allowing users to review ACRO outputs and approve or reject them for release, with comments, and (c) generating release packages for download containing only approved outputs.

Functional testing is structured around these core steps. We perform testing using both bundled toy examples provided with the viewer and additional inputs generated through our ACRO testing above. Using these inputs, we use the viewer to visualise all the examples (toy and generated by us), and go through the workflow of steps (a) to (c) above to comment on, approve or reject outputs, and release output packages. We include at least one example of every type of analytical output currently supported by ACRO.

The focus here is on the review process within the viewer for a single user. We then discuss extension to workflow scenarios described at Section 3.2 above.

3.3.1. Focus on positive testing

The SACRO Viewer itself doesn't perform any checking and is only designed to work with ACRO-generated .json files and outputs. Our main focus is therefore on testing that the UI behaves as expected given valid, ACRO-generated inputs and correctly displays the ACRO results. This includes testing that the viewer correctly excludes non-approved outputs from the release package. Note that, as part of ACRO testing, we test whether ACRO .json files contain correct information about the attached outputs and disclosure checks. This is not tested again as part of the viewer assessment.

We do more limited negative testing focused on replicating or modifying ACRO-generated outputs and testing whether the viewer correctly identifies these as modified. While it also is possible to e.g. modify files to invalidate inputs to the viewer, we do not perform this testing and instead prioritise positive testing. This is mainly because there are limited scenarios under which invalid inputs could occur. ACRO outputs are subject to testing/validation upstream, and any changes to outputs post-ACRO are highlighted as 'modified'. This reduces the likelihood of invalid inputs significantly.

3.3.2. Non-functional testing

In addition to functional testing, we perform non-functional testing in a similar manner to testing for ACRO. That is, we set out key questions around ease of use (including ease of installation, navigation and completing checks), documentation support and sustainability / suitability for the Ronin TRE. Testing and evaluation against these key questions is performed by members of the Panorama project team, across SDEs, familiar with the research and output checking process.

3.4. Summary of testing results

Details of testing and findings can be found at Appendix B. Overall, we found the viewer to have very few issues and functionality works as expected for a single user:

- Positive functional tests using bundled toy examples passed except for one issue. Specifically, tabular outputs did not display all relevant variable names (see [Table B1](#)). Otherwise, the viewer correctly displayed outputs and .json file contents.
- One functional issue was also identified from additional ACRO-generated outputs. Specifically, it appears the viewer cannot correctly render ACRO-generated pivot-tables with more than one indexing layer. However, rather than raising an error (i.e. not displaying a table at all), the viewer displays the tables with incorrect red-flagging. (See [Table B1](#) for further details.)
- The viewer correctly packaged up outputs for release. The user can also see relevant information around each statistical check, including checking parameters applied.

- One SDE observed, however, that not all information in the .json files that was relevant to reviewers was displayed in the UI. Specifically, the command that was run to generate the output was hidden from the UI. This meant in practice it was necessary to examine the .json file directly while reviewing. (See [Table B2](#) for further details.) Further, reviewing could be better supported by more information being included in the report to improve auditability and more complex checking. For example, information on source data or grouping outputs by source data would be useful to provide more complete logging of activity.
- Where ACRO outputs are modified, the viewer correctly identifies this as being the case and displays this to the user - we see this as a useful feature in an end-to-end workflow. Similarly, the viewer won't process ACRO-like outputs that were not generated via ACRO.
- Non-functional tests show that the viewer is mostly very user friendly. It is straightforward to install and use, there is no configuration required, and it is well supported by documentation. Further, it is feasible to use and maintain within the environment with no problematic dependencies.
- We note, however, that additional steps were required to install the viewer in an airlocked environment and admin privileges were required for installation but not for usage. For testing installation was done by users with sufficient privileges, but in the future a portable version would be very useful. Longer term, PANORAMA partners indicated they could add SACRO tools to the standard workspace image, which will avoid user installation.
- One key usability issue is that work is not saved if the user exits the application and there is no option to save partially complete reviews. So, all output checking for a set of results must be completed in a single session. This would also extend to e.g. system failures / stopping of the TRE environment. This could be a significant limitation in the adoption of SACRO tooling for reviewers. As mentioned above, researchers may process outputs in small, frequent batches for initial checking. However reviewers may prefer, or be required to, process outputs via large, infrequent requests, depending on resourcing and operating procedures.
- Finally, one potential maintenance issue going forward is that some dependencies are old (but not deprecated) and the viewer is not actively maintained in terms of versions. However, the open source repository has active contributors, so some maintenance is occurring (mainly in the documentation).

In the process of testing the SACRO-Viewer, a number of other features were identified that are not currently supported but which would be very useful to scaling usage to larger workloads and/or extending their use to the multi-user, multi-step workflow described at Section 2.2 above. These include support for commenting and approving across multiple outputs together, tracking multiple output packets in the review pipeline and their status and supporting tracking and sharing between users. Currently tracking must be done outside of the tool, however providing this functionality would allow users to streamline their process and improve auditability.

3.5. Recommendations

Given the ease of use of the viewer and straightforward installation, our recommendations are mainly around functionality supported and ensuring compatibility between ACRO and SACRO-Viewer.

1. We suggest that tests / bundled examples for the viewer be expanded in line with ACRO methods supported. This will ensure that issues such as that above (the incorrect rendering of multi-index tables) are minimised and there is continued alignment of viewer and ACRO functionality and development.
2. Further, it would be desirable to tie version releases of the viewer to ACRO versions, or at least clearly cross-reference in the documentation the ACRO version supported by the viewer.
3. Further development of reviewer-oriented features to the SACRO-Viewer, in particular:
 - a. Progress tracking within and across multiple output bundles
 - b. Support for multiple users to interact around the same output bundle
 - c. Ability to save and return to partially completed reviews.

4. End-to-end testing

4.1. Introduction

The purpose of end-to-end testing is to evaluate how tools perform in the context of the end-to-end pipeline as follows:

(a) generating analysis in ACRO → (b) saving ACRO outputs → (c) loading outputs into SACRO-Viewer → (d) reviewing outputs in SACRO-Viewer → (e) releasing and exporting outputs via SACRO-Viewer.

We perform some 'light touch' end to end testing in addition to separate testing of each tool. We test the full pipeline by following steps (a) to (e), taking outputs generated via ACRO as described in Section 2 on ACRO testing, saving, loading and evaluating them in SACRO-Viewer before exporting them. We consider both non-functional aspects for the user workflow, and functional aspects, specifically additional testing of SACRO-Viewer on more outputs. Outputs cover a more complete set of methods (and their variations) not covered by the toy examples bundled with SACRO-Viewer.

Non-functional workflow aspects are focused on ease of completing the full workflow for a single piece of analysis including

- selecting or finding file locations
- whether ACRO outputs (not bundled examples) seamlessly load into the viewer

Functional aspects, focused on expanded testing of ACRO outputs in the SACRO-Viewer, follow the same methodology as for toy example testing in the SACRO-Viewer. Where issues arise, these are noted below, but also in the relevant ACRO/Viewer sections above.

We note that the workflow process and control around the tools is manual. There is no direct linkage between the tools and no automatic or enforced passing of outputs from ACRO to SACRO-Viewer. This also extends to egress control (exporting outputs out of the TRE environment), which are dependent on the TRE configuration, and passing outputs between researchers and reviewers.

Testing structure and results for non-functional tests only are provided at [Appendix C](#) (See [table C1](#)) - functional testing results are added to results for ACRO and SACRO-Viewer as

appropriate. The following sections give an overview of the testing areas and approach, and summarise key findings.

4.2. Summary of testing results

Non-functional testing confirmed that the end to end process is straightforward and generally seamless for a user. Users specify an output location when generating ACRO output, then can potentially simply select that location in the Viewer to start the review process. Except for isolated issues listed below, all outputs from ACRO were successfully processed in the Viewer without any further steps being needed.

Expanded output testing of the viewer identified a small number of functional issues. Specifically:

- One method available in ACRO was not fully supported by the viewer, specifically the `pivot_table` method where tables had multi-level indexes. The viewer currently appears to only support pivot tables with single-level indexes (equivalent to `cross_tab`).
- When calling ACRO `finalise()` twice successively for the same outputs, an error occurs when outputs are viewed in the Viewer. Specifically, the Viewer is unable to display any of the outputs in the folder (all output file types are read as 'custom' rather than e.g. '.csv'). The source of the error was not identified, but may be due to automated file name errors and changes to the .json file generated in ACRO.

4.3. Recommendations

Overall, as also discussed at Section 3 above, the end to end process highlighted that more coordinated testing between the viewer and ACRO could be useful. While an issue such as e.g. viewer support for more comprehensive ACRO outputs can be addressed through more testing of the viewer, other issues such as file names and version management for individual outputs across the pipeline may be highlighted through coordinated testing.

End to end testing also underscored that, in order to integrate SACRO into a workflow involving more than one person, many steps have to occur outside the tooling, including requesting review, passing output files between tools and people, returning files where re-work and re-review is needed, and tracking versions and status of multiple outputs in the pipeline. Further thought could be given to whether SACRO could extend support to status and process tracking to facilitate this. One idea, for example, is an internally hosted web-based application with appropriate API and governance controls.

5. Output checking in a federated network

Whilst the previous section of the report has focussed on (semi-) automated tools that could be introduced to improve the speed and transparency of output checking, parallel real-world consultation with those involved in output checking focussed on the operational requirements to enable federated output checking. The PANORAMA research team facilitated interviews with output checkers within PANORAMA and with TRevolution Early Adopters VISTA and SOCRATES to develop detailed Federated Output Statistical Disclosure Control (OSDC) Principles designed to support consistent, safe, and scalable federated analytics across TREs. Developed through lived experience of practitioners, cross-organisational consultation, and analysis of current practice, the framework highlights the substantial operational complexity

involved in conducting SDC, particularly when multiple organisations collaborate as part of a federation.

The Federated OSDC Principles (provided as a separate document) outlines the foundational decisions that organisations must collectively address, such as choosing a federation model, aligning minimum thresholds and suppression methods, determining whether an Aggregator is required, and deciding how (semi-)automated tools like SACRO may be incorporated. Central to the guidance is the recognition that while federated analytics offers clear benefits for governance, data sovereignty, and scalability, differences in SDC rules, risk tolerances, processes, and operational capacity can present major barriers to successful federation. Without deliberate agreement on approaches and processes, federated projects risk inconsistent outputs, uneven disclosure protections, and significant delays.

The document ultimately demonstrates that SDC is not a simple technical step but a resource-intensive operational function that varies substantially across organisations. These operational realities must be confronted directly; failure to do so could lead to incompatible release decisions, increased disclosure risk, or unmanageable workload across the federation. The Federated OSDC Principles therefore provides a structured basis for organisations to surface differences, negotiate shared standards, and plan for the practicalities of implementing SDC at scale. This includes consideration of how tools like SACRO could support federated SDC processes.

Overall, the Federated OSDC Principles underscores that federated SDC requires careful planning, sustained collaboration, and explicit operational design. Without such preparation, the benefits of federation could be undermined by substantial operational friction and the potential for significant negative consequences in both security and service delivery.

6. Could SACRO Serve as a ‘Set of Eyes’ in the Four Eyes Principle?

6.1. The Four Eyes Principle

The ‘Four Eyes Principle’ is an established governance mechanism to ensure that no data that could potentially identify an individual will be released from a TRE by requiring two independent checks of analysed data. Traditionally, this involves two human reviewers assessing risks of disclosure, consistency with SDC policies. As TREs face increasing pressures on capacity, and as federated research networks amplify the volume of outputs requiring review, PANORAMA aims to consider whether semi-automated tools such as SACRO could serve effectively as one of the ‘set of eyes’ in this process.

6.2. Potential benefits of SACRO’s use in the Four Eyes Principle

A potential benefit of using SACRO is improved consistency and standardisation. SACRO applies a set of codified SDC rules consistently across outputs, reducing variation that can arise in manual checking due to differences in individual judgement, experience, or interpretation. As one set of eyes, SACRO could provide a standardised baseline check, ensuring that high-risk issues (e.g. small cell sizes, potential dominance in tabulations, or high-risk plot types) are flagged reliably before a human reviewer completes their assessment.

Another potential benefit is improved reviewer efficiency. By automating checks for common and well-defined disclosure risks, SACRO can reduce the cognitive load on human checkers, enabling them to focus their expertise on complex or ambiguous cases. In a Four Eyes workflow, SACRO could perform the first pass, allowing the human reviewer's time to be concentrated where their judgement is most valuable.

A third potential benefit is auditability. SACRO produces clear, reproducible evidence of the rules it applies and the conditions under which a warning or failure is triggered. This supports robust audit trails and strengthens governance assurance. Using SACRO as one of the sets of eyes ensures that the first stage of checking is documented and repeatable, contributing to transparency in decision-making of releases.

A final benefit is that SACRO may be scalable if used in the same way within federations. In federated analytics, outputs may need to be reviewed across multiple environments with varying local policies and workload constraints. SACRO may help harmonise part of the review process, providing a common baseline across TREs. Incorporating SACRO into the Four Eyes Principle could reduce bottlenecks and promote interoperability in multi-TRE workflows.

6.3. Considerations and limitations

Although SACRO is effective for predefined SDC rules, many disclosure-risk scenarios require contextual interpretation – for example, understanding the nature of the underlying study population, the sensitivity of variables, or risks arising from combining results across outputs. SACRO cannot yet assess these contextual nuances and therefore cannot be considered a 'set of eyes' in the fullest sense and must be paired with a human reviewer who remains ultimately responsible for the release decision.

SACRO's rule set is intentionally focused on common output types and therefore has coverage limitations. Novel statistical models, bespoke graphics, narrative text, or non-standard representations will fall outside its scope. In a Four Eyes process, SACRO's contribution will be partial or unsupported for some outputs.

Introducing automation into a governance workflow carries the risk that human reviewers may become overly reliant on the tool, potentially overlooking issues outside SACRO's capabilities. Studies in other disciplines that use the Four Eyes Principle have shown that there are biases introduced with respect to experience levels (De Vries et al., 2023) and towards AI (Dratsch et al., 2023). In the [Semi-Automated Risk Assessment](#) (SARA) project, members of the public expressed concerns about overreliance on colour coding (e.g., 'red' or 'green'). The public were concerned that colour coding implies an obvious fail/pass and that 'green' (passes) would simply be approved without examination of the contents and that potentially disclosive contents might not be picked up by the 'green' automation. This finding from other research should be explored in detail in relation to SACRO to examine further in future iterations of the SACRO viewer. Clear guidance, ongoing training, and appropriate oversight would be necessary to ensure SACRO enhances (rather than weakens) human decision-making.

Finally, as discussed in the previous section, federated systems may have differing disclosure policies between organisations. SACRO's rules can be tuned, but alignment across TREs is required before using SACRO as a component within the output checking workflow. Without agreement between the federated network, SACRO could either under- or over-flag outputs relative to local expectations.

6.4. Assessment

SACRO can act as an initial ‘set of eyes’ in specific instances, particularly for researchers using it as a ‘guardrail’ to highlight basic SDC issues. It provided structured, consistent checks where researcher analysis fits within the automation. However, SACRO cannot currently function as a full substitute for a human reviewer.

- The most appropriate use for SACRO at this stage of its development is that of a ‘supporting eye’ - performing systematic checks where it can support output checking that complement but should not replace human oversight.
- Governance frameworks would need to specify clearly how SACRO’s assessment interacts with the ultimate responsibility of human reviewers.

A possible model at the current stage of SACRO development:

1. Researcher prepares their outputs using ACRO and checks the outputs using the SACRO viewer.
2. Researcher packages all outputs including SACRO viewer outputs and submits an egress request to the TRE SDC team.
3. Eye 1: Output Checker 1 reviews the egress request using SACRO viewer as a tool in evaluating the request. .
4. Eye 2: If Output Checker 1 agrees that outputs can be egressed, Output Checker 2 reviews outputs, with or without SACRO..

With further development, a plausible model for OSDC using SACRO could be:

1. Researcher prepares their outputs using ACRO and checks the outputs using the SACRO viewer.
2. Researcher packages all outputs including SACRO viewer outputs and submits an egress request to the TRE SDC team.
3. Eye 1: Output Checker 1 re-runs the egress request with SACRO performing automated SDC checks and producing a structured report.
4. Eye 2: If SACRO indicates that the egress can proceed, a human reviewer (Output Checker 2) evaluates the output, considering both SACRO’s findings and contextual factors outside the SACRO automation’s scope.

This hybrid model preserves the integrity of the Four Eyes Principle while gaining the efficiency and standardisation benefits of semi-automation, but does require substantial additional development.

7. Conclusion

This work has provided a detailed assessment of SACRO—specifically the ACRO library and SACRO Viewer—and its potential role within a federated output-checking ecosystem. Across functional, non-functional, and end-to-end evaluations, the tools demonstrated strong performance for core use cases and clear potential to support more efficient, auditable, and standardised Output Statistical Disclosure Control (OSDC) in Trusted Research Environments (TREs). ACRO performed reliably for supported analytical methods, offering valuable guardrails for researchers and consistent application of disclosure-control rules, while SACRO Viewer

provided an accessible and intuitive interface for review and release decisions. Together, the tools offer a viable semi-automated workflow that could reduce manual workload, support consistency, and strengthen governance.

However, the assessments also highlight important limitations. ACRO currently covers a restricted set of analytical functions, with several edge-case behaviours—particularly around suppression, complex tables, and histogram generation—that require refinement. SACRO Viewer, while robust for standard cases, showed issues rendering certain multi-indexed tables and in handling repeated finalisation outputs. Some usability limitations in tracking and saving progress, particularly for large volumes, were also identified.

More broadly, neither tool yet addresses multi-output disclosure risk, contextual interpretation, or the operational variance that exists across federated TREs. The operational research conducted alongside the technical testing reinforces that federated OSDC is not solely a technical challenge but an organisational one: without shared principles, aligned thresholds, and coordinated processes, even well-designed semi-automated tools cannot fully resolve inconsistencies or scale effectively across a federation.

Finally, while SACRO could contribute meaningfully as part of a Four Eyes workflow, it cannot currently replace a human reviewer. Its ability to provide consistent and auditable checks makes it a strong candidate for a “supporting eye,” but contextual judgement and nuanced risk assessment remain firmly reliant on human expertise.

7.1. Recommendations for Future Work

To build on the progress demonstrated in PANORAMA Work Package 3 and to support the maturation of SACRO within both standalone and federated contexts, we recommend the following areas for future development:

7.1.1. Tool Development

- Enhance robustness and flexibility of ACRO’s analytical methods, particularly around suppression logic, multi-index tables, and histogram behaviour, ensuring consistent output generation across a wider range of realistic research scenarios.
- Expand ACRO analytical coverage, prioritising high-value additions (e.g., broader model classes, more flexible visualisations) informed by common use cases across TREs.
- Introduce multi-output risk assessment, enabling SACRO to evaluate disclosure risk across sets of outputs rather than one at a time.
- Strengthen SACRO Viewer compatibility by increasing bundled test coverage, aligning versioning explicitly with ACRO releases, and improving rendering for complex tables.

7.1.2. Workflow, Integration, and Usability

- Conduct coordinated end-to-end testing across tool versions, ensuring interoperability and early detection of cross-component bugs such as naming conflicts or rendering errors.
- Add reviewer-oriented workflow features to SACRO Viewer, including dashboards, progress tracking, and improved metadata navigation.
- Explore deeper automation within TRE workflows, for example optional linkage between ACRO output generation and SACRO Viewer ingestion, while maintaining appropriate governance controls.

7.1.3. Governance and Federated Operation

- Further develop and operationalise the Federated OSDC Principles, including practical templates, decision guides, and exemplar workflows to support TREs in aligning standards and processes.
- Pilot SACRO within real federated projects, testing the tool under realistic workload, policy-alignment, and cross-organisation operational conditions.
- Evaluate SACRO's role within the Four Eyes Principle in live settings, examining impacts on reviewer workload, consistency, and potential risks such as over-reliance or misinterpretation of automated flags.
- Develop training, guidance, and calibration materials to ensure that SACRO's outputs are interpreted appropriately and that automation enhances (but does not fully replace) human decision-making.

This work demonstrates that SACRO has the potential to significantly strengthen output-checking workflows in both individual TREs and federated environments. Realising this potential will require continued technical development, coordinated governance, and focused efforts to address operational complexity. However, with this ongoing development, SACRO could form a key component of scalable, safe, and consistent federated analytics across the UK research ecosystem.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Appendix A: ACRO testing details

This appendix sets out detailed testing conducted and results for ACRO, including data inputs, specific functional and non-functional evaluations and issues identified.

All testing was performed on a virtual machine with a University of Sheffield Ronin Core environment unless otherwise noted. The virtual machine had the following specification: Ubuntu 22 as operating system, 8 core cpu and 32 GB of RAM.

A.1 Data and Models

The main dataset used for the analysis is a Heart Disease prediction dataset provided by Kaggle (<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/rishidamarla/heart-disease-prediction>). It was chosen because it provides a valuable prediction for the models (heart disease), it is pre-processed, with different data types and is relatively small and easily manipulated. The dataset contains the following variables:

Table A1: Test dataset variables (Heart Disease)

Variable	Data type
Age	int64
Sex	int64
Chest pain type	int64
BP	int64
Cholesterol	int64
FBS over 120	int64
EKG results	int64
Max HR	int64
Exercise angina	int64
ST depression	float64
Slope of ST	int64
Number of vessels fluro	int64
Thallium	int64
Heart Disease	object

The dataset consists of 270 entries. An example of the Heart Disease dataset is shown below.

	Age	Sex	Chest pain type	BP	Cholesterol	FBS over 120	EKG results	Max HR	Exercise angina	ST depression	Slope of ST	Number of vessels fluro	Thallium	Heart Disease
0	70	1	4	130	322	0	2	109	0	2.4	2	3	3	Presence
1	67	0	3	115	564	0	2	160	0	1.6	2	0	7	Absence
2	57	1	2	124	261	0	0	141	0	0.3	1	0	7	Presence
3	64	1	4	128	263	0	0	105	1	0.2	2	1	7	Absence
4	74	0	2	120	269	0	2	121	1	0.2	1	1	3	Absence

Figure A1: example of the heart disease prediction dataset used in testing.

In order to test survival analysis functions, we also make use of the Veterans Lung Cancer dataset provided by scikit-survival (sksurv). The dataset originates from a randomized clinical trial comparing two treatment regimens for lung cancer in veterans, and it contains data that can be used for survival analysis. The dataset contains the following variables:

Table A2: Test dataset variables (Lung Cancer)

Variable	Description	Data type
Status	Whether the patient died (True/False)	Boolean
Survival_in_days	Number of days until death	Float64
Treatment	Test vs. Standard therapy	Object
Celltype	Category of lung cancer cell type (4 types)	Object
Prior_therapy	Whether patient had earlier treatment	Object
Age_in_years	Patient age	Float64
Karnofsky_score	Functional health status (higher = better)	Float64
Months_from_Diagnosis	Time since diagnosis to study entry	Float64

The dataset consists of 137 entries. An example of the Lung Cancer dataset is shown below.

	Age_in_years	Celltype	Karnofsky_score	Months_from_Diagnosis	Prior_therapy	Treatment	Status	Survival_in_days
0	69.0	squamous	60.0	7.0	no	standard	True	72.0
1	64.0	squamous	70.0	5.0	yes	standard	True	411.0
2	38.0	squamous	60.0	3.0	no	standard	True	228.0
3	63.0	squamous	60.0	9.0	yes	standard	True	126.0
4	65.0	squamous	70.0	11.0	yes	standard	True	118.0

Figure A2: Example of Veterans lung cancer dataset.

A.1.1 Manipulating Core Dataset

The majority of testing is conducted using the above datasets in their original form. To conduct additional tests for negative testing around missing values and incorrect types, we manipulate selected cells or variables in the above datasets to be either NaN or string data types. Separately, to test large dataset handling, we artificially increase the number of rows for the Heart Disease dataset.

A.2 Functional Testing Outcomes

This section sets out detailed tests and results for functional testing, covering four main functional areas: installation, configuration, generating analyses with and without suppression, and outputting analyses with disclosure checking evaluations. The latter two groups cover testing of ACRO methods, described below.

A.2.1 ACRO Methods

ACRO currently provides a number of analytical methods and several non-analytical methods relating to e.g. export of outputs and disclosure checking reports. The following table summarises the core methods (more comprehensive information can be found in the [SACRO API documentation](#) online).

Table A3: Summary of the core methods (analytical and non-analytical) provided by ACRO

Method	Description	Key Variations / Options
Analytical methods		
crosstab	Generates a cross-tabulation of two or more variables from observational tabular data (defaults to a frequency table) Wrapper for Pandas	1. Summary using different aggregation functions via aggfunc() (supporting mean, median, sum, std, count, mode) Include row/column subtotals Normalise values (convert counts to proportions)
pivot	Create a spreadsheet-style pivot table as a dataframe i.e. a multi-index dataframe. Contains summary data (defaults to generating a summary table of means). Zero and NaN rows/columns are always excluded Wrapper for Pandas	Summary using different aggregation functions via aggfunc() (supporting mean, median, sum, std, count, mode) Include row/column subtotals
hist	Generate histogram for 1D (single-variable). Automatically exports as a .png image file. Wrapper for Matplotlib with limited support for Matplotlib graphing kwargs.	By_val - Splits histogram into groups of other columns. E.g histogram of Cholesterol `by_val`=Sex, will plot one hist for men and one for women
Ols / olsr	Fits 1D OLS model from standard numeric tabular data olsr - takes in data array with model formula rather than exog and endog args Wrapper for statsmodels	Treatment of missings. Missings can be ignored, dropped or raise an error (default ignore).
Logit / logitr	Fits logit model from standard numeric tabular data (exog and endog variables) logitr - takes in data array with model formula rather than exog and endog args Wrapper for statsmodels	Treatment of missings. Missings can be ignored, dropped or raise an error (default ignore).
Probit / probitr	Fits probit model from standard numeric tabular data (exog and endog variables) probitr - takes in data array with model formula rather than exog and endog args Wrapper for statsmodels	Treatment of missings. Missings can be ignored, dropped or raise an error (default ignore).

Survival functions	Surv_func - Computes an empirical survival function from tabular data including time variable (returns survival table or plot) Survival_plot - generate plot of survival probability by time Survival_table - generate table of survival probability by time Wrapper for statsmodels	Optional entry times ('included from') and frequency weights - these affect survival proportion estimates.
Non-Analytical methods		
Add comments	Add a comment to a specific output	-
Add exception	Add exception to a specific output. Exception is an explanation of why an output should be approved, although it didn't pass acro's tests.	-
Print outputs	Print all the outputs that have been generated for acro. Usually used before finalise().	-
Remove output	Remove a specific output from acro's queue.	-
Rename output	Rename an output	-
Finalise	Generate the output folder for the outputs in the queue	-

The methods above are attached to the `acro` class, the main class with which users interact. ACRO package also has another class, the `record` class, which stores data related to a collection of output records. This is not for end users to utilise in their normal workflow. The class offers only very limited additional functionality for users so is excluded from testing below.

A.2.1 Functional Testing Results

The table below sets out core ACRO functional areas and detailed testing conducted for each area, with outcomes. This includes execution of all the ACRO class methods above with and without suppression applied, plus installation and configuration.

Table A4: ACRO functional testing schedule and observations

ACRO functional testing schedule		
Function	Test Description	Results
<p><i>Installation</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - users can install ACRO package - users can import ACRO package in a python notebook/script 	<p>Follow steps in user guide to install ACRO package in a python environment along with other standard python packages</p> <p>Imported ACRO into Jupyter notebook along with other standard python packages and instantiated an instance of ACRO class.</p>	<p>Installation, import and instantiating class were completed with no issues identified.</p>
<p><i>Configuration</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - users can customise output checking parameters - users can update output checking parameters - users can view output parameters 	<p>Attempt to customise and update output checking parameters by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) defining a config dictionary and passing into ACRO class 2) directly amending the config file (default.yaml) 3) creating a new config .yaml file <p>NB Testing pull-through of correct output checking parameters to individual methods is completed in method testing below.</p>	<p>Configuration parameter setting</p> <p>It was possible to set custom output checking parameters, however some issues were identified.</p> <p>Issue 1: parameter setting by config dictionary argument to class instance is not functional.</p> <p>Although the documentation here states that you can change the configuration by using a variable, in practice ACRO returned an error. The only way found to change the configuration was to amend or replace default.yaml file within <code>`~/python3.13/site-packages/acro`</code> folder. The documentation does not appear to provide the location or instructions for amending/replacing this file.</p> <p>Issue 2: documentation not updated with correct default value for <code>`safe_nk_k`</code></p> <p>The ACRO documentation here states that the default value of <code>`safe_nk_k`</code> parameter is 0.85 but in the default .yaml file it is set to 0.9 .</p> <p>Users are able to view checking parameters upon instantiation of the acro class.</p>
Analytical Methods without Suppression		
<p><i>Analytical Methods - generating analysis without suppression</i></p>	<p>For each analytical method we conducted a positive test using the data described above. We also conduct spot tests (limited set of methods) for</p>	<p>Results against each test set are shown against the relevant method in the table rows below. NB: This part of the table shows results without suppression applied.</p>

ACRO functional testing schedule		
Function	Test Description	Results
- users can call analytical methods to correctly generate analysis and results for each of the following methods	<p>negative testing with input data changed to include (a) missing values then (b) invalid data types.</p> <p><i>Negative test design</i></p> <p>1. Missing values Tabular output: Values for `EKG results`-`Cholesterol` for 20 randomly selected rows were set to NaN. Tables were generated with and without suppression for crosstab and pivot_table. Models: To test whether the regression models correctly adjust the degrees of freedom when dealing with missing values, all values of 5 random rows were set to NaN.</p> <p>2. Incorrect data types 'EKG results' and `Cholesterol`, which are both numeric columns, were changed to string types. For survival analysis the timestamp was set to string and float. Tests were conducted with and without suppression for analytical and non analytical methods.</p>	Results with suppression applied are shown separately below (see table section for `Analytical Methods without Suppression`)
Table generation	<p><i>Crosstab:</i> Generate summary table using crosstab, for each agg_func() supported, with and without normalisation. Inputs: Heart Disease prediction dataset with different combinations of column-pairs Compare outputs to the same table generated directly in pandas without ACRO wrapper.</p> <p>Negative testing: Generate summary table using crosstab (no suppression), for count and mean. Inputs: Sex-EKG results-Cholesterol columns of Heart Disease dataset.</p> <p><i>Pivot:</i></p>	<p><i>Crosstab:</i> Without suppression, values are correct. No issues with method were detected</p> <p>Negative testing - missing values: Values are correct and acro ignores missing values without any errors or unexpected behaviour. Also, if `aggfunc` is set to `mean`, acro correctly calculates the mean values. Negative testing - wrong data type: ACRO correctly counts string values for the `count` aggfunc, and returns an error when `aggfunc` was set to mean and `Cholesterol` was changed to string. This is consistent with other python package handling of missing and `wrong` types.</p> <p><i>Pivot:</i> Without suppression, values are correct. No issues with method were detected.</p>

ACRO functional testing schedule		
Function	Test Description	Results
	<p>Generate a multi-index dataframe using up to two (one) levels of indexing for rows (columns), for each agg_func() supported.</p> <p>Compare outputs to the same table generated directly in pandas without ACRO wrapper.</p> <p>Negative testing: Generate summary table using pivot table (no suppression), for count and mean.</p> <p>Inputs: Sex-EKG results-Cholesterol columns of Heart Disease dataset.</p>	<p>Pivot negative testing results were as for cross_tab. Missing values and wrong data types were handled as expected.</p>
<p>Histogram generation</p>	<p>Generate histogram for all available columns in the dataset using several different values for bin count.</p> <p>Generate using two columns by passing an extra column into 'by_val'.</p> <p>Generate using 'grid', 'xlabelsize', 'ylabelsize', 'xrot' and 'yrot' parameters.</p> <p>Negative testing: Generate histogram for 'Cholesterol' which had some missing values.</p>	<p>Histograms generated as expected without issues.</p> <p>All the design manipulations worked as expected.</p> <p>Negative testing - missing values: Histogram was generated without any issues. Values are correct and ACRO correctly ignores missing values without any errors or unexpected behaviour.</p>
<p>Statistical model fitting</p>	<p>NB: ACRO does not automatically add a constant to the model and tests were conducted without a constant.</p> <p>OLS</p> <p>Positive testing: Models fitted using 'Cholesterol' as dependent variable and 'Max HR' ('Age') as independent value for ols() (olsr())</p> <p>Negative testing (OLS only): Models fitted using 'Cholesterol' as dependent variable and 'Age', 'BP' as independent values for ols().</p> <p>Logit</p> <p>Models fitted using</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 'Heart Disease' as dependent variable and 'Max HR, Cholesterol' as independent value for logit() and logitr() 	<p>Model results generated as expected and no issues were detected.</p> <p>NB the default behaviour in ACRO differs from the default behaviour of underlying packages with respect to adding a model constant. This is different to the usual approach in statistical packages but is highlighted in the ACRO documentation.</p> <p>Negative testing: Models were built without any errors, despite the missing values, when 'missing' parameter was set to 'drop'. Acro correctly got rid of the missing values and built the models. When 'missing' was set to 'raise' or 'None' (default), acro correctly returned an error.</p>

ACRO functional testing schedule		
Function	Test Description	Results
	<p><i>Probit</i></p> <p>- `Heart Disease` as dependent variable and `Max HR, Cholesterol` as independent value for <code>probit()</code> and <code>probitr()</code></p>	
Survival analysis	<p>Surv_func fitted using `Survival_in_days` and `Status` variables. The arguments of `entry` and `freq_weights` were not tested.</p> <p>Survival_plot and survival_table outputs generated using the same data / results as for surv_func.</p>	Survival analysis results generated as expected and no issues were detected.
Analytical Methods with Suppression		
<p><i>Analytical Methods - generating analysis with suppression</i></p> <p>- relevant parameters are applied for each method</p> <p>- outputs with suppression correctly generated</p>	<p>For each of the tests applied above without suppression, we repeat generation of outputs but with suppression. Each config parameter is tested for at least two different values.</p> <p>Negative testing: All the negative tests conducted for the functions without suppression were conducted also with suppression.</p> <p>NB: Testing excludes mathematical evaluation of parameter relevancy to different methods. Rather, relevancy is taken from ACRO source code and documentation (and sense checks).</p>	<p>Results against each test set are shown against the relevant method in the table rows below.</p> <p>Note on parameter updates: As noted at the top of this table, parameter updates must be done by amending/replacing the default.yaml config file. To apply parameter updates, users must then re-instantiate the ACRO class and re-call the relevant method.</p>
Table generation	<p>Generate tables as for non-suppressed versions above.</p> <p>Check that the correct version of config parameters is pulled through and applied to outputs.</p> <p>Check risky table cells are suppressed.</p> <p>Check potentially disclosive subtotals and total are suppressed.</p> <p>Complete for positive and negative tests as above.</p> <p>Crosstab relevant suppression parameters: count, p-ratio test and nk test</p>	<p><i>Crosstab</i></p> <p>Functionality is as expected except for two issues. Correct parameter values are pulled in and applied in suppression.</p> <p>Issue 1: When suppress was set to `True`, margins was set to `True` and at least one of the column names passed to the class included a space character (e.g `Chest pain type` contains two spaces), an error occurred.</p> <p>Specifically, if crosstab has to suppress a cell, it returns an error about the column name due to being unable to parse a logical string used in the suppression logic</p>

ACRO functional testing schedule		
Function	Test Description	Results
	Pivot relevant suppression parameters: count, p-ratio test and nk test	<p>that includes spaces. This only occurs when some cells need suppression. E.g. the variable pair ['Sex', 'Chest pain'] will trigger this error.</p> <p>Issue 2: When `suppress = True` and `normalize` is not set to `False`, Acro always returns a table full of NaN's. It's not clear why this occurs, but it may be related to the order in which suppression/normalisation is applied, and/or normalisation propagating NaN values.</p> <p>NB `normalize` can take the values [True, False, 'all', 'index', 'columns', 0, 1].</p> <p><i>Pivot</i> Suppression works as expected and no issues were detected.</p>
Histogram	<p>Tested generation for all the numeric columns of the dataset with number of bins autogenerated and manually generated. Bin values tested for Heart Disease dataset = [3,4,8,10 (default),15,25].</p> <p>We also tested with custom bin boundaries.</p> <p>Histogram relevant suppression parameters: safe_threshold</p>	<p>Output failed to generate with suppression applied and bins automatically generated.</p> <p>This appears to be due to some bins containing values below safe thresholds, resulting in the whole histogram not being output, rather than e.g. bin list being amended under the hood to exclude risky bins. The generation of bins with zero values is the main reason this occurred.</p> <p>For `suppress = True` the histogram was only successfully generated for this dataset when the number of bins was manually set to be very small or with custom boundaries. However both these options are not practical for research.</p> <p>This is in contrast to the equivalent frequency table (non-normalised), where non-suppressed rows will be shown.</p>
Statistical models	<p>Test for low degrees of freedom</p> <p>All the models included in `Statistical model fitting` were tested for correct flagging when they have degrees of freedom below the threshold (relevant parameter: safe_dof_threshold). Both increasing the degrees of freedom threshold and decreasing the degrees of freedom of the models by adding independent values and removing rows were tested.</p>	<p>Acro's behavior was aligned with the expected results, by correctly flagging all the models that fell below the defined degree of freedom threshold.</p> <p>For negative tests, models were built without any errors, despite the missing values, when `missing` parameter was set to `drop`. Acro correctly got rid of the missing values and built the models. When `missing` was set to `raise` or `None`,</p>

ACRO functional testing schedule		
Function	Test Description	Results
	Negative testing - missing values (OLS only): Models fitted using `Cholesterol` as dependent variable and `Age`, `BP` as independent values for ols().	acro returned an error. Also, acro suppressed the models that had degrees of freedom below the threshold taking into account missings.
Survival Analysis	Test for number at risk threshold. Survival function was tested for correct flagging of rows in a survival table that have a change on `number at risk` below the `survival_safe_threshold` threshold, by increasing and decreasing the `survival_safe_threshold`.	Acro was correctly identifying, flagging and suppressing all the `number at risk` changes that were below the threshold without any issues or errors.
Non-analytical methods		
<p><i>Non-analytical Methods</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - users can update (add and remove) analytical outputs from the final list to be exported - users can add free text to outputs (comments and exception requests) - users can export analytical outputs with .json report - users can export alternative, human-readable reports (.xlsx) 	<p>All the non-analytical methods were tested under a realistic workflow scenario after generating the analysis above and covering at least one example from each analytical method (most outputs generated above were ultimately checked through the full process). The methods tested were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● add_comments() ● add_exception() ● remove_output() ● rename_output() ● finalise() <p>Checks:</p> <p>Report file generates correctly.</p> <p>Report files, or results file, contain the information about the output results of each function and about the suppressed values (e.g which values were suppressed by acro, which test fails).</p> <p>Flags are correct for config settings.</p> <p>The user can select the report format, including all options stated in documentation (i.e. .json, .xlsx)</p>	<p>All the .json outputs generated by acro had no issues and they were flagging the correct values.</p> <p>Everything worked as expected when trying to make changes on the outputs and when finalising them. Acro was successfully making all the relevant changes to the outputs and no issues were encountered. Except in two scenarios.</p> <p>Issue 1 - calling finalise() twice successively</p> <p>One unexpected behavior was observed when calling finalize acro a second time right after calling it. The expected outcome would be either to display a message like 'no outputs to finalize', or to generate the exact same output folder as the last finalization.</p> <p>Although acro generates a new output folder with all the files that were included in the previous finalization, that folder is not properly processed by SACRO-Viewer.</p> <p>More specifically, SACRO-Viewer reads all the output files as `Custom` type and cannot locate the files generated for the same output (e.g output_1_0 and output_1_1) resulting in processing them as separate outputs.</p> <p>This did not occur in every case but the exact trigger for this error was not identified.</p>

ACRO functional testing schedule		
Function	Test Description	Results
		<p>A screenshot (FigureA3) from what appears in SACRO-Viewer when processing outputs generated after re-running finalize() is included below.</p> <p>Issue 2 - .xlsx currently not supported</p> <p>The second unexpected behaviour was observed when acro is finalized) with `ext` set to -xlsx . Although acro generates an output folder that contains the results.xlsx file, the folder doesn't include the several output files and SACRO-Viewer doesn't process it or read it.</p> <p>The .xlsx file does not appear to be currently supported (potentially an encoding issue).</p>

Figure A3: SACRO-Viewer homepage when processing outputs generated after calling finalize() twice. (Outputs are read as 'custom' type and unable to be displayed.)

A.3 Non-Functional Testing Outcomes

As described in Section 2 of the report, non-functional testing considers practical aspects for researchers - ease of installation and use, documentation support, sustainability and operability in the relevant (Ronin) environment, and support for key use cases for researchers. The table below sets out key non-functional areas and evaluation against each. Testing and evaluation was performed by University of Sheffield and Yorkshire & Humber SDE team members familiar with research requirements and their counterparts in North East North Cumbria and North West SDEs. Results shown are for University of Sheffield/Yorkshire & Humber in the first instance with differing and additional results included from other SDEs.

Table A5: Non-functional testing results and observations

Non- functional area	Test Results and Observations
<p><i>Installation and operation in UoS (Ronin Core)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Version control and compatibility with operation environment</i> 	<p>Acro is currently maintained with new versions and updates. The package after extensive testing works fine in both Ubuntu and Linux images that Ronin provides.</p>
<p><i>Getting started</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Ease of installation and surfacing within Python</i> - <i>Ease/difficulty of setup and adjustment to key disclosure configuration settings</i> 	<p>Very easy to install through pip.</p> <p>Researchers only need to be careful with the location of the installation, if not done inside jupyter, as python generally virtual environments for the projects.</p> <p>Very easy to setup and configure. Once it's installed, the user only needs to instantiate the acro class.</p> <p>However, one limitation was identified regarding user setting of checking parameters. This was described above in functional testing (Table A.4 (Configuration)). Users must locate and directly alter or replace the .yaml file to set custom checking parameters and this is not supported by documentation.</p> <p>Preferably, these could be set without needing to access the file.</p>
<p><i>Usability</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Ease/difficulty of functional use for researchers</i> - <i>Documentation support for researchers</i> 	<p>Very easy to use for researchers that are familiar with python and data analysis libraries. It has the same syntax to popular libraries, like pandas, and doesn't require any further training on how to use it as long as you are familiar with python.</p> <p>Lastly, it provides details about the supported programming languages and the supported environments.</p> <p>The documentation covers all of the information that an average user will ever need. It has details about all the functions/classes that acro supports along with fully working examples of an average workflow that the user would follow. Also, it provides all the relevant</p>

	information on how to install, configure and initialize an instance.
<i>Performance on large datasets</i> - <i>Methods execute on larger datasets in reasonable time</i>	<p>Acro worked seamlessly when tested with datasets up to one million rows for the same analytical methods as tested on the original dataset.</p> <p>Performance tests showed that acro does not add any major computational complexity to the libraries that it wraps no matter the dataset size. Acro's methods were tested using datasets with 1000, 10,000, 100,000 and 1,000,000 rows and all of them were completed instantly (less than a second).</p> <p>ACRO methods did take longer than the underlying functions that it wraps from other packages, for selected methods where ACRO and the underlying function were compared. Specifically, for Pandas wrappers, ACRO took roughly double the time to generate outputs for the largest examples (still only 0.2sec).</p>
<i>Sustainability</i> - <i>Sustainability and any dependency on non-maintained packages</i>	All the dependencies of acro are popular python libraries that are actively maintained.

A.3.1 Installation in airlocked environments

For airlocked environments, support of an internal package repository mirror for pip installation of python / R is required for ACRO installation. For organisations using mirrors, no issues arose around installation.

Other airlocked environments may make use of a reverse proxy solution to PyPI / R-Cran for their repositories. We did not test this solution but do not anticipate installation issues.

Appendix B: Testing SACRO Viewer

SACRO Viewer comes bundled with example .json output checking reports (in the same format as would be generated by ACRO) along with associated analytical outputs generated via the ACRO class methods detailed above. Specifically, the Viewer includes toy examples for the following methods: crosstab, pivot_table, ols(r), probit and logit.

In addition to bundled examples, we also tested SACRO Viewer with examples generated through our ACRO testing. This expands the set to include all analytical methods in ACRO and key variations, with and without suppression.

Results of SACRO Viewer functional testing across all example inputs are shown at Table B1 below.

As for ACRO, we also conducted a non-functional evaluation of the viewer around ease of installation, usability, documentation support and integration into a research-reviewing workflow.

Results for non-functional testing are shown at Table B2.

B.1 Functional Testing Outcomes

Table B1: SACRO Viewer functional testing schedule and observations

Core functional area	Test Results
<p><i>Reading in ACRO outputs</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Viewer can process .json script from ACRO - Viewer displays checking results in .json script correctly - Viewer displays associated analysis (outputs) correctly 	<p>The bundled .json file was loaded and contents in the file checked against displayed results in the viewer. Contents of the file were then modified to test whether displayed outputs updated accordingly.</p> <p>All results were displayed correctly and correct cells in tabular outputs were shown as flagged except for two issues:</p> <p>Issue 1 - tabular output variable names not displayed Not all variable names for tabular outputs are displayed when tables are displayed in the viewer. For crosstab, only one of two names is shown, and for pivot_table multi-index tables (with three variables) only two of three names were shown.</p> <p>Issue 2 - multi-index pivot tables not rendered correctly The viewer did not correctly render pivot tables with more than one indexing layer. The viewer displays the tables with incorrect cells red-flagged as containing risky values (rather than raising an error). The source of the error seems to be flag indexing contained in .json report files currently only supporting single-index pivot tables.</p>

<p><i>Reading 'invalid' inputs into the viewer</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - altered inputs - non-ACRO inputs ('ACRO-like') 	<p>Tested by (a) modifying values directly in tabular output .csv files produced by ACRO and (b) copying ACRO-generated files (creating 'ACRO-like' inputs) and trying to view them in SACRO-Viewer.</p> <p>The viewer displayed the modified data, regardless of whether it was a valid input type, however for results modified, the SACRO-Viewer flagged the output as 'modified' with a prominent warning.</p> <p>For ACRO-like inputs, these were tagged as a 'custom' type and could not be displayed and processed in the viewer.</p>
<p><i>Checking outputs for release</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User can approve or reject individual outputs for release - User can add comments for either approval or rejection (individual outputs or combined) - User can check configuration parameters used to generate ACRO checking results 	<p>Approve/Reject buttons and commenting box were tested for each output. The viewer does not support shared commenting across outputs.</p> <p>All functions behave as expected and no issues were detected.</p> <p>Configuration parameters are displayed when first selecting a folder of results to examine on the homepage, and above each individual output</p>
<p><i>Egress of outputs and checking results</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User can export approved outputs - User can export checking report (approved and non-approved outputs) - User cannot export non-approved outputs 	<p>Release and downloading buttons tested after processing individual outputs.</p> <p>Users can first select 'Release and download' and in a second step select 'download approved outputs' and/or 'download review summary'.</p> <p>Confirmed approved outputs package excludes non-approved outputs, however this does not enforce any control over non-approved outputs on its own (see next comment)</p> <p>NB: The 'download' function in the Viewer does not download from the secure environment but exports a clean set of approved outputs to a location selected by the reviewer.</p> <p>Both outputs submitted for checking and the approved, exported outputs are potentially on the same Ronin image. Controls around read/write access to/from different locations and egress from the secure environment depend on the environment configuration (not the Viewer).</p>

B.2 Non Functional Testing Outcomes

The table below sets out key areas and questions for non-functional testing, along with associated responses and observations.

Table B2: Non-functional testing results and observations

Non- functional area	Test Results and Observations
<p><i>Installation in Ronin</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can the viewer be installed in Ronin? - Was the documentation from SACRO sufficient for installation (was augmentation required)? - Was the amount of troubleshooting required for installation reasonable for a typical researcher? 	<p>Yes, the viewer was relatively straightforward to install in Ronin especially in Windows with minimal troubleshooting.</p> <p>The only thing missing was some dependencies on Ubuntu because the Ronin image is very light and comes only with the minimum numbers of applications (just Mozilla installed with snap and vim).</p> <p>Documentation online was sufficient to support typical users to install in Windows. For Ubuntu some additional instructions may be needed to install dependencies.</p> <p>One SDE (NENC) noted that admin privileges are required for installation (but not use), so <u>providing a portable version would be useful</u>. For Ronin Core, the viewer is installed in a project virtual machine (for which users have sufficient privileges to install) however this will differ across SDEs. See comments below on installation in airlocked environments.</p>
<p><i>Getting started</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - how easy was it to open and get started? - Was documentation support sufficient for a typical researcher? - Was the configuration reasonable for a typical researcher? 	<p>SACRO-Viewer comes preconfigured. It's very reasonable and easy to launch the application and get started.</p> <p>Once launched the user just needs to select the folder that contains the output files of ACRO to use SACRO-Viewer.</p> <p>Further configuration is required only in ACRO if the researcher wants to change the default values of the disclosure tests.</p>
<p><i>Navigation and Usability</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - how easy was it to navigate around the tool and understand core functionality? - how easy was it to execute the core functions? - how easy was it to complete the reviewing workflow within the viewer? 	<p>The navigation is very easy as long as the user understands exactly what output checking is and the role of SACRO-Viewer.</p> <p>Core functionality is logical and easy to use however one limitation was noticed during testing:</p> <p>Issue 1 - Relevant information in the .json report is not displayed in the UI.</p> <p>Reviewing the command executed to generate the output was found to be very useful but this is only in the .json (not displayed in the UI). One SDE (NENC) noted it was necessary to keep returning to the .json for key information and that reviewing commands could be very useful for extension to joint disclosure risk checking.</p>

	<p>The reviewing workflow could be easily completed by a single user within the Viewer, however the following limitations were noticed around the workflow:</p> <p>Issue 2 - Review must be completed in a single session. All work is lost when exiting the application so the whole review process must be completed in a single session for a set of outputs. This is quite limiting since it's not possible to process outputs in batches in multiple sessions and any disruption could mean progress is lost.</p> <p>Issue 3 - Review must be completed by a single user Following from Issue 2, the tool does not currently support multi-user reviews. This is limiting for scaling to larger and more complex output checking, where task-splitting and conferral between reviewers may be needed.</p>
<p><i>Sustainability</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Is the viewer dependent on any old or deprecated packages?</i> - <i>Is it easy to update versions / is it being actively maintained?</i> 	<p>Some dependencies are old but not deprecated. There is only one version available. The viewer is not actively maintained in terms of versioning but there are still people committing to the repo, mainly in docs. This might lead to errors in the future if dependencies and operating systems evolve.</p>

B.2.1 Installation in airlocked environments

As for ACRO, installation of SACRO-Viewer in airlocked environments required some extra steps, specifically running the installer outside of the airlock, then zipping the installed SACRO-Viewer files before passing to a secure workspace via airlock. The viewer can then be run in the secure environment. While extra steps were required, no other issues arose during installation and operation.

Longer term, all SDEs participating in Panorama indicated they would add both ACRO and SACRO-Viewer to standard workspace images, which would avoid manual installation.

Appendix C: End-to-End testing

As described in Section 4 above, we completed ‘light touch’ end to end testing of the SACRO tools in an end-to-end process, where we first generate outputs in ACRO then review them in the Viewer. This focused on (a) limited non-functional testing around ease of taking outputs from ACRO and into the viewer, and (b) utilising functional testing in ACRO (see Appendix A) and testing through the full pipeline using the viewer.

Results for functional testing using expanded outputs in ACRO and the viewer are included within functional testing results in Appendices A and B above. As described above, some additional functional issues came to light through this process that were not identified when testing tools individually.

Table C1 below sets out results for non-functional testing of the end to end pipeline. A broader discussion around workflow outside and around the tooling is contained in the main report (see Sections 4 to 6).

Table C1: End-to-End non-functional testing results and observations

Non- functional area	Test Results and Observations
<i>How easy is it to complete all steps in the generate - export - view workflow for a single piece of analysis?</i>	It's relatively easy, especially for researchers that are familiar with python and popular data analysis tools. Once the dataset is loaded in the python environment, ACRO stores all the generated outputs automatically (the user only has to finalise the output once s/he is done with the analysis). After finalising, acro creates a folder with all the outputs, which can then be then loaded to the viewer for inspection.
<i>How easy is it to export outputs from ACRO for import into SACRO? I.e. - saving outputs of each step to suitable location and finding them from that location</i>	Very easy. You only need to call <code>acro.finalise(` /desired location folder')</code> and acro will generate a folder with all the outputs inside the selected path. For sacro viewer, you just need to select that folder when starting the application in order to import it.
<i>Was any fixing needed of outputs from ACRO before they could be properly ingested / processed by the viewer</i>	No. All the outputs generated during testing were directly processed by Sacro-viewer without any changes.